

Person Centered Care

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The term “patient centered medicine” was coined in 1969 by the psychoanalyst Enid Balint¹. This approach understands the patient as a unique human being and considers the patient as a whole instead of having a narrow focus on the condition or symptoms only. It is in contrast to “illness-oriented care” which is aimed at finding a localizable fault, diagnosing it as an illness and then treating it. Over the years, the terminology has symbolically shifted to “person centered care”. The word “person” is used to emphasize a holistic approach in which the person's personal preferences, wellbeing and social and cultural background are also given due importance.

In person centered care, the health professionals work in collaboration with the person requiring medical services. It enables the people to acquire knowledge, skills and confidence which helps them to make decisions and manage their own health care more effectively. It is tailored to the requirements of the individual. Crucially, it ensures that people are treated with compassion, dignity and respect.

The concept of person centered care does not have a single agreed definition as it involves many different principles. It is also because the concept is still emerging and evolving. In addition, the person centered care depends upon the needs, preferences and circumstances of the individual requiring care. Instead of offering a concise and limited definition, the Health Foundation (UK) has identified four principles of person centered care²:

1. Dignity, compassion and respect
2. Coordinated care or treatment
3. Personalized care or treatment
4. Supporting the people to develop their own abilities and strengths, enabling them to live a fulfilling and independent life.

Any example of person centered care, should have a combination of these principles. The fourth principle,

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enabling care, differs from others. The health care provider can uphold other three principles on his own without the recipient's input. However, for the care to be enabling, the healthcare professionals and patients have to build up a relationship and work together to:

- Understand what issues are important to the person
- Make decisions about the modalities of care and treatment
- Identify their goals and try to achieve them

In addition to the obvious ethical rationale for adopting person centered care, there are also a number of very practical reasons. Many people would like to have a more active role in healthcare. There is increasing evidence that person centered care, which incorporates shared decision making as well as support for self management, can improve patient's satisfaction and quality of care³. Individuals who acquire more knowledge, confidence and skills to manage their healthcare, engage in positive health behaviors to a greater extent which results in better health outcomes. Person centered care is also good for health care professionals. Their morale and performance increases with the increase in patient engagement.

Is person centered care affordable?

This approach ensures that resources are spent on what actually matters to the people. Patients get the opportunity to make decisions of their treatment according to their own preference. The healthcare professional will not prescribe any medicine that the patient will not take, or refer them for any services that they will not avail or advise any surgery that they will not have⁴. Hence, it will save any potential waste of time or financial resources.

Does person centered care save money?

There is evidence of cost saving. For example:

- Better informed people often choose treatments which are less expensive and less invasive⁵.
- People who are trained to manage their own care are less likely to use hospital emergency services⁶.
- They are more likely to adhere to their treatment plan and take their medicines as advised.

Adopting person centered care requires important

changes in delivery of health services. American psychiatrist George Engel promoted this move in the late 1970s. The principles of person centered care were incorporated in the health care in USA during the 1990s, when Chronic Care Model was developed to support people with long term conditions. In 2001, the Institute of Medicine USA added “patient-centeredness” as one of its six aims of healthcare. Over the following years, the ideas of “person-centeredness” started to appear regularly in UK health policy⁷. Today person centered care is central to the health policies of the four countries of UK. Ultimately all levels of healthcare system have to play an important role in creating the proper conditions for person centered care to flourish. They include local and national policymakers, organizational leadership as well as the patients and service users. Making this shift is a challenging process which requires effort, but it is certainly possible.

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